

was added to a well stirred solution of II (0.05 mol) in dry benzene/dioxane (50 ml). The mixture was refluxed for 4 h. The excess solvent was removed and the solid mass washed with aqueous sodium carbonate solution (10%) and finally recrystallised from petroleum ether or benzene. The melting points and other data of the compounds are recorded in Table 2.

Antibacterial screening: Agar plate diffusion technique¹⁴ was employed for the determination of antibacterial activity of the synthesised compounds of type II and III against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus pumilus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Bacillus branchi-septice*, and *Sarcina lutea*. The results are given in Table 1 and 2.

The antibacterial activity of both the series seems to be sporadic with no apparent pattern and thus making it difficult to correlate with structural requirements.

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Synthesis and Antimicrobial Evaluation of 1-(Phenyl/methylcarbamoyloxyphenyl)-2-methyl/phenyl-4-(substituted benzylidene)-5-imidazolone, A New Class of Carbamates†

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A number of 1-(hydroxyphenyl)-2-methyl/phenyl-4-(substituted benzylidene)-5-imidazolone and their *N*-methyl and *N*-phenyl carbamates have been synthesised and evaluated for their antimicrobial activities against a number of bacteria and fungi.

The biological properties associated with *N*-methyl, *N,N*-dimethyl and *N*-phenyl carbamic esters of various alcohols and phenols have been reported¹⁻⁴. In continuation of our interest towards the synthesis of potential antimicrobial agents^{5,6}, we hereby report the synthesis of the title carbamates according to the sequence of reaction outlined in Chart 1 with a view to study their antimicrobial efficacy. The choice of imidazolone derivatives arose because their number of analogues have been shown to exhibit diverse types of biological activities including antibacterial properties.

Chart 1

Various 2-methyl/phenyl-4-(substituted benzylidene)-5-oxazolone (1-5), obtained by the condensation of acetyl/benzoylglycine with several aryl aldehydes, on reaction with various aminophenols in pyridine, furnished 1-(hydroxyphenyl)-2-methyl/

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NOTES

phenyl-4-(substituted benzylidene)-5-imidazolones (6-20). The ir spectra of 6-20 showed strong bands at 1650-1640 (C=N), 1690 (C=O) and 3225 cm⁻¹ (OH). The pmr spectrum of 8 showed signals at 7.34-7.75 (m, 9H, ArH), 6.70 (s, 1H, PhCH=), 2.24 (s, 3H, CH₃) and 8.20 (s, 1H, OH, exchangeable with D₂O), whereas a thirteen proton multiplet of compound 19 was observed at 7.00-7.55 along with a singlet of three protons at 3.80, assigned to -OCH₃. The spectra and integrations are consistent with the proposed structures.

Refluxing 6-20 with methyl/phenyl isocyanate in dry benzene or THF in presence of triethylamine yielded the title carbamates (21-41). The ir spectra showed bands at 1680 (C=O of imidazoline), 1700-1690 (C=O of CONH), 1645 (C=N of imidazolone) and 3320 cm⁻¹ (NH). The pmr spectrum of 29 showed signals at 7.25-7.68 (m, 19H, ArH), 6.8 (s, 1H, PhCH=), 12.25 (m, 1H, NHCO, exchangeable with D₂O). The spectrum was featureless in the methyl and methylene proton region. Additional signals in the methyl region at 3.82 and 2.78, in the spectrum of 37, were assigned to OCH₃ and N-CH₃ protons. In the spectrum of 23, a pair of three proton signals at 2.36 (s) and 2.82 (d) were assigned to CH₃X₂ protons in different chemical environment.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The ir spectra were obtained on a Perkin-Elmer Infracord 137 and pmr spectra on a Varian A-60D instrument using CDCl₃ as solvent and TMS as an internal standard (δ scale). The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc on silica gel G plates.

2-Methyl/phenyl-4-(substituted benzylidene)-5-oxazolones (1-5): A suspension of acetyl/benzoyl glycine (0.01 mol) in acetic anhydride (5 ml) was warmed on a sand bath till all the solid dissolved. After cooling, the reaction mixture was poured into absolute ethanol containing anhydrous sodium acetate (3.0 g) and appropriate aldehyde (0.01 mol). The flask was transferred to a water bath and heated for about 4 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and the resulting solid was filtered and recrystallised from CCl₄ or ethyl acetate.

1-(Hydroxyphenyl)-2-methyl/phenyl-4-(substituted benzylidene)-5-imidazolones (6-20):

Method A: A mixture of each of 1-5 (0.01 mol) and respective aminophenol (0.01 mol), in dry pyridine (10 ml), was refluxed on a sand bath for 5-8 h under absolute anhydrous conditions. Excess of pyridine was removed by distillation. The concentrated mass was cooled and dissolved in minimum ethanol and poured in excess of ice-cold water. The solid mass thus obtained was thoroughly washed with cold water, followed by petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°), filtered and recrystallised from appropriate solvent (Table 1).

TABLE 1—1-(HYDROXYPHENYL)-2-METHYL/PHENYL-4-(SUBSTITUTED BENZYLIDENE)-5-IMIDAZOLONES (6-20)

Compd. no.	R	R ¹	Position of heterocyclic	M.p. °C
6	H	OH ₂	2	119
7	H	CH ₃	3	157-8
8	H	CH ₃	4	123
9	H	C ₆ H ₅	2	141
10	H	C ₆ H ₅	3	214
11	H	C ₆ H ₅	4	219
12	p-Cl	OH ₂	2	129
13	p-Cl	CH ₃	3	187
14	p-Cl	OH ₂	4	249-50
15	p-Cl	C ₆ H ₅	2	199
16	p-Cl	C ₆ H ₅	3	245-6
17	p-Cl	C ₆ H ₅	4	237-8
18	p-OCH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	2	236
19	p-OCH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	3	238-9
20	p-OCH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	4	259-60

Compounds no. 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 8, 12, 13 recrystallised for methanol; 6, 7, 10, 11, 14 recrystallised for methanol/water; 9 and 15 purified by dissolving in 4 N NaOH and precipitating with 2 N HCl.

Compounds no. 1 and 4 prepared by both the methods were identical (m.p., m.m.p., ir and ca tlc). Others were obtained by method A only.

All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

Method B: A mixture of each of 1-5 (0.01 mol) and respective aminophenol (0.01 mol) was fused at 160-70° (oil bath) for about 2 h under anhydrous condition. The crude hydroxyphenyl derivatives of imidazolone thus obtained on cooling were recrystallised from appropriate solvent (Table 1).

1-(Phenyl/methylcarbamoylphenyl)-2-methyl/phenyl-4-(substituted benzylidene)-5-imidazolones (21-41): A solution of appropriate phenol (6-20) (0.01 mol) in dry benzene or THF was added portion wise to a 5 to 10% excess of phenyl/methyl isocyanate. After the addition was complete, 2-3 drops of triethylamine was added and the mixture was refluxed for a period varying from 2-20 h. The product was isolated by concentration of the reaction mixture *in vacuo* with subsequent agitation of the residue to induce crystallisation. The carbamates were recrystallised from appropriate solvent and their melting points and analytical data are presented in Table 2.

Antimicrobial activity: The *in vitro* antibacterial activity of compounds 6-41 was determined against *B. pumilus*, *S. aureus*, *S. lutea*, *E. coli*, *B. subtilis*, *B. megaterium*, *B. cereus* and *B. polymyxa* at a dose level of 200 µg/0.1 ml following the method of Varma and Imam⁷. Antifungal activity was studied against *H. sativum*, *A. terreus* and *A. niger* at three different concentrations, viz. 1:1000, 1:10000 and 1:100000 following the method of Horsfall⁸.

The antibacterial activity of these compounds especially 14, 16, 19, 24 and 37 against *B. pumilus* had activity equal to that of standard compounds (sulphonamides and antibiotics) whereas marginal activity of these compounds was obtained against

TABLE 2—1-(PHENYL/METHYL CARBAMOYLOXYMETHYL)-2-METHYL/PHENYL-4-(SUBSTITUTED BENZYLIDENE)-5-IMIDAZOLONES (21-41)

Compd. no.	R	R ¹	R ²	Position of heterocyclic	M.p. °C
21	H	OH ₂	CH ₃	2	108
22	H	OH ₂	OH ₂	3	122
23	H	OH ₂	OH ₂	4	118
24	H	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	2	197
25	H	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	3	220
26	H	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	4	231-2
27	H	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	2	154
28	H	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	3	206-7
29	H	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	4	186
30	p-Cl	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	2	111-2
31	p-Cl	OH ₂	C ₆ H ₅	3	198
32	p-Cl	OH ₂	C ₆ H ₅	4	142-3
33	p-Cl	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	2	137-8
34	p-Cl	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	3	177
35	p-Cl	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	4	186
36	p-OCH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	OH ₂	2	140
37	p-OCH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	OH ₂	3	138
38	p-OCH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	OH ₂	4	109
39	p-OCH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	2	187-9
40	p-OCH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	3	178-9
41	p-OCH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	4	158

Compounds no. 16, 20 and 25 recrystallised from benzene and the rest from benzene petroleum ether.

All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

S. aureus and *E. coli*. Out of the compounds evaluated, 14 and 24 showed inhibition against all the bacteria. Regarding antifungal activity, four compounds, viz. 23, 25, 32 and 38 were effective against *A. terreus*, while only compounds 32 and 41 were effective in inhibiting the growth of *H. sativum*. All the compounds are active at higher concentrations and activity decreases markedly on dilution. Rest of the compounds were not active against any of the three species of fungi.

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Chemical Examination of the Leaves of *Woodfordia fruticosa*

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WOODFORDIA fruticosa kurz.¹ (syn. *Woodfordia floribunda* Salisb) (Lythraceae) a beautiful much branched shrub with brilliant scarlet flowers, is very common in North India but scarce in Orissa and South India. Leaves of this plant are used for dying and tanning purposes². Besides, the leaves possess antibiotic^{3,4} as well as sedative⁵ properties.

The presence of naphthaquinone⁶, polyphenols⁷ and traces of alkaloid⁸ in the leaves were reported earlier. The present communication deals with the isolation and identification of triterpenoids and sterol in the leaves. The plant material (450 g) collected from Simlipal forest, Orissa, was exhaustively extracted with rectified spirit in a Soxhlet Extractor. The alcoholic extract was concentrated under reduced pressure. The dark coloured semi-solid mass obtained was separated into ether soluble and ether insoluble parts. Ether soluble part was then separated⁹ into acidic and neutral fractions.

The total acid fraction (0.21 g) was chromatographed over silica gel. Elution with CHCl₃:methanol (98:2) yielded a crystalline material showing one major and another minor spots in tlc (silica gel, CHCl₃, visualized with L-B reagent) which were separated by preparative tlc. The major compound on repeated crystallisation from methanol afforded betulinic acid as shining needles (11 mg), m.p. 310-312°. It yielded an acetate as plates, m.p. 291-293°, identical with authentic acetate of betulinic acid⁹ (m.p., m.m.p., ir). On methylation with diazomethane it gave a methyl ester (m.p. and m.m.p. 221-222°).

The minor compound was identified as oleanolic acid by comparative tlc with authentic oleanolic acid and by m.p. (308-310°). Further work could not be done due to paucity of material.

Chloroform:methanol (96:4) eluted another crystalline material (silica gel, CHCl₃:EtOAc 1:1, single purple spot with L-B reagent). It crystallised from methanol as needles (92 mg), m.p. 279-282°, [α]_D+64° (c 0.41 in CHCl₃); acetate m.p. 289-290°, [α]_D+60° (c 0.31 in CHCl₃); methyl ester m.p. 170° identical with authentic methyl ursolate¹⁰ (m.p., m.m.p., ir).

The neutral fraction was chromatographed over neutral alumina. Petroleum ether:benzene (1:1) eluted lupeol (100 mg) m.p. 210-211°, [α]_D+22° (c 2.0 in CHCl₃), acetate m.p. 209-211°, [α]_D+44° (c 0.37 in CHCl₃); benzoate m.p. 251-61°. Finally the identity was established as lupeol by comparison with authentic lupeol (m.p., m.m.p., ir). Benzene eluted β-sitosterol (38 mg), m.p. 136-137°; acetate m.p. 128°, [α]_D-35° (c 0.29 in CHCl₃); benzoate m.p. 144°. Identity of β-sitosterol was